
Teachers' Classroom Management Skills at the Elementary Stage in the Era of Education 5.0 (NEP 2020)

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ABSTRACT

Classroom management is a fundamental process of teaching and learning, especially at the primary level. Children are in a crucial stage of cognitive, emotional, and social development. Well-maintained classes provide students with an eco-friendly classroom where they feel comfortable, secure, and motivated. This type of classroom provides a cooperative and friendly environment where they focus on the learning process and develop positive behaviour. This research paper provides information related to classroom management by teachers at the elementary level. This paper discusses the concept, nature, importance, objectives, principles, and dimensions of classroom management. The paper further examines essential classroom management skills, challenges faced in classroom situations, strategies adopted by teachers, and educational policies in strengthening their skills, Education 5.0 (NEP 2020). The paper concludes that classroom management skills are indispensable for elementary teachers and play an important role in improving the quality of education.

Introduction-

Education plays a vital role in shaping individuals and society. Among all the level of education, elementary education took a fundamental position as this education develop personality and its going life

long. In this stage, students acquire basic literacy and numeracy skills, social values, habits and attitudes. Elementary education largely depends on the effective classroom environment, learning environment, and teaching quality. Classroom is not only a physical space, but it is also a social environment where different backgrounds, abilities and behaviours interact. Managing diversity requires effective classroom management, which refers to the techniques and strategies used by teachers in their teaching and learning process. Students learn and adopt things when the classroom becomes secure, effective and organised.

What is Education 5.0?

Education 5.0 is modern model of education where it focuses on both technology and human values. It's main objective are all over development in children not only education.

In simple words, Education 5.0 is equal to technology along with empathy, ethics , creativity, and responsibilities.

According to Kounin (1970)

Effective classroom management focuses on preventing misbehaviour rather than reaching to it. Modern classroom management emphasises proactive, student-centred, and supportive practices.

Nature of Classroom management

- Learning is continuous process as well as life long process.
- It should be more flexible and dynamic
- Holistic development is must in every student.
- Teaching should be student centered.
- Find problems on advance and creating organized way for engaging routines to prevent misbehaviour.

Objective of Classroom management

- Classroom have proper desk and benches.
- Blackboard and whiteboard is must in every class.
- Proper ventilation
- To create safe amd supportive learning environment.
- To maintain discipline in the class and reduce disruption as it is not good learning process.
- Use teachings time very well.

- Motivate and give reinforcement to students in each activities.
- To develop self discipline among students and also social skills.
- Promoting positive teachers-students and peer relationship.
- Encouraging active participation and student engagement.

Importance of Classroom management

Classroom management is must at elementary stages as they are new learner so they require routine, structure and guidance to feel secure and confidence. Effective classroom management help in both academics and non-academic outcomes. It also important for emotional and social development of students .it directly affects students' academic performance.

Some important points of classroom management are-

- Classroom management help in enhancing teacher-student relationship.
- It provides safe environment and promotes inclusive environment.
- If classes maintain in effective way then it reduces disruption and Distraction.
- It enhances teaching and encourage student responsibility and self-regulation.
- It also increases time on task.

An effective classroom is very important because it is associated with students' achievement, reduces dropouts, helps students in their performance, increases motivation and lowers incidents of Classroom misbehavior.

Key Classroom Management skills for elementary teacher

1. Effective communication –

- Communication is the root of classroom management. Teachers must use language appropriate for age and level.
- Provide clean instruction.
- Give them feedback.
- Always reinforce and motivate students.
- Listen actively and respectfully.

2. Behaviour management techniques

- Teachers must use appropriate language.

- Setting clear expectations.
- Monitoring behaviour of students consistently.

3. Instructional planning and Organization

- Teachers must have prepared lesson plan, or unit plan for teaching because well planned lessons correlate with better classroom control so they should prepare lesson plan before teaching in the class.
- Use time effectively.

Features of Education 5.0

1. Human Centered Education – it's focuses on learner centered education, not syllabus.

- Here every student are different from each other.
- Teachers understand the feeling of students.
- There is understanding environment not discipline dear.

2. Technology + values-

- Use of smart class and digitalization tools.
- It explain about moral values ,ethics and respect.
- No misuse of technology.
- It help students to use technology in right way.

3. Emotional and social development

- It help students to control their feelings.
- It emphasizes on teamwork, empathy and cooperation.
- It also provides safe and positive environment in classroom.

4. Creativity and critical thinking

- It provides learning by doing instead of rote learning.
- It's focuses on activities, projects and problem solving skills.
- Here students become innovator along with learner.

5. Life skills and Responsible citizen

- As a responsible citizen of our country, student and teachers should take good decision and healthy decision.
- Maintain self discipline.
- Perform social responsibility.

Relation between Education 5.0 with Classroom management

Classroom management in Education 5.0-

- It promotes a healthy and free environment instead of Punishment.
- It promotes understanding, guidance, and motivation.
- Teachers become mentor or facilitators instead of dictator.
- Teachers teach students about self-discipline.
- Teachers should use positive reinforcement for students.

Role of Teachers training and professional Development

For elementary teachers, there are a lot of organisations that work for teachers' training, such as government (NCTE, NCERT, SCERT, DIET, CBSE), autonomous (NIEPA, NIOS), and International (UNICEF, UNESCO) organizations.

A teacher's education program must include classroom management training. Professional development is-

- Practical workshops
- Peer mentoring
- Reflective practice

Research findings suggest that teachers who received systematic training in classroom management exhibit higher confidence level, display great self assurance and enhance teachers confidence and improve the effectiveness of their classroom practices. Training demonstrate stronger confidence and superior management skills.

Challenges

At the elementary level, Classroom management is a complex and demanding task because children at this phase are in the early phases of their emotional, social, cognitive and behavioural development. Every student is different from each other, such differences are- interest, learning speed, family background and their capacities, etc. These differences create problems for teachers.

Major challenges are-

1. Mixed ability levels

Here, the presence of children with varying ability levels within the same class. Some children have good grasping power. They grasp concepts quickly, while others require repeated explanation.

2. Behavioural disorders and emotional issues

At the elementary level, there are a lot of students who display behavioural challenges such as lack of attention, hyperactivity, aggression or impulsivity. Conditions such as ADHD (Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder), Anxiety, or emotional disturbance. So proper training is must for teachers.

3. Large class size

A large classroom creates an obstacle to Effective classroom management. Teachers struggle to provide individual attention, monitor student behaviour and maintain discipline consistently. A crowded classroom leads to increased noise levels, distraction and reduced student engagement.

Linkage of NEP 2020, Education 5.0 and Classroom Management

National Education Policy 2020 deeply linked with Education 5.0 because both focuses or emphasizes on Holistic, Learner centered, Inclusive and Value base education. NEP 2020 and Education 5.0 redefine classroom management as supportive, development oriented and inclusive process rather than a rigid and control-based system.

Education system in 21st century is Seeing remarkable changes due to rapid technological development, Change in social needs and Human centered learning.

In this context Education 5.0 is modern model of education that include new ideas along with value based, emotional, intelligence and moral values. Unlike earlier educational models that focuses basically on knowledge transmission (Education 1.0) or skill development and digitalization (Education 3.0 and 4.0).Education 5.0 emphasizes personalized learning, empathy, creativity and holistic development of learners.

NLP (Natural language processing) is main technological enabler for Education 5.0 , NLP is part of AI (Artificial intelligence) that enables machines to generate human language, understanding and interpretation. NLP tools are Speech recognition, sentiment analysis, text analysis, Chatbots and automated feedback systems have opened new outcomes in teaching learning process.

This technology not only enables the teaching learning process, but also plays the main role on classroom management especially at elementary level.

Classroom management is an important part of effective education, where students are in a sensitive stage of cognitive development, emotional development and social level. Effective classroom management emphasizes on cooperative and motivated learning environment.

Traditional classroom management depends on disciplined, rules and punishment based but Education 5.0 demands a shift toward proactive, learner centred and emotionally responsible classroom management where students' emotion, language and behavioral pattern becomes essential.

The connection between Classroom management and NLP tools within the boundaries of Education 5.0. It focuses on Empathy, Data informed, Decision making and communication. It helps teachers to understand students' emotional states through their spoken or written language such as classroom discussion, reflective journaling or digital interactions. When teachers identify stress, confusion or disengagement earlier then they adopt preventive classroom management strategies, reducing behavioural problems and enhancing student well being.

From a Classroom management perspective such tool promotes effective classroom management and effective teaching. It reduces classroom disruption and fosters a positive learning climate. NLP tools support reflective and data driven Classroom management. As we know NEP 2020 emphasizes on multilingualism, experiential learning, formative assessment and inclusive education and here NLP tools provide support in managing elementary classroom. It helps classroom practices from control oriented to human centric and intelligent empathetic management.

Experiential learning and activities based management

NEP 2020 focuses on elementary and foundational stages and emphasizes experiential, activities based and play based learning for elementary and foundational stage. Education 5.0 strengthens the creativity, innovation, real life and problem based.

Classroom management strategies –

- It manages movement based activities effectively.
- It organizes group work and collaboration tasks.
- Ensuring safety and engagement during experiential learning.

Inclusive and equitable classroom management

NEP 2020 and Education 5.0 emphasizes on both inclusive and equity. Here teachers should maintain classroom according to learners from diverse social cultural backgrounds , language and abilities.

Competency Based Assessment and Classroom Management

NEP 2020 emphasizes on competency based learning instead of rote learning while Education 5.0 supports reflective, continuous and growth oriented evaluation.

Impact on class –

- It helps to reduce anxiety and exam related stress among students.
- It encourage motivation especially intrinsic motivation.
- It treat fearless classroom environment.

Ethical, Emotional, and Value based Classroom Environment

NEP 2020 emphasizes on ethical, emotional, and value based classroom environment where Education 5.0 is a defining aspect of philosophy.

Teachers manage classroom by –

- Teachers should teach empathy, cooperation, and responsibility.
- Teachers should encourage communication instead of Punishment.

Conclusion

Classroom management is essential for the success of elementary education. It plays a vital role in determining the overall effectiveness of elementary education. At the elementary level, students not only acquire knowledge but also develop social, emotional, and behavioral skills.

An effectively managed classroom becomes holistic child development. Without proper classroom management, even well-designed curriculum management is not limited to maintaining discipline well educated, creative teacher so teacher training is must at every level of education.

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